

What can we learn from confusing *Olivella columellaris* and *O. semistriata* (Olivellidae, Gastropoda), two key species in panamic sandy beach ecosystems?

A.I. TROOST, S.D. RUPERT, A.Z. CYRUS, F.V. PALADINO, B.F. DATILO, W.S. PETERS

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Definition and descriptions of the two *Pachyoliva* species in older texts and recent identification keys

This document reviews the literature that is pertinent to the definition and identification of *Olivella semistriata* GRAY 1835 and *O. columellaris* SOWERBY 1825, the two species that form the subgenus *Pachyoliva* OLSSON 1956.

The document consists of three parts.

1. **Original diagnoses of the two *Pachyoliva* species**, by [1.1.] Sowerby (1825) and [1.2.] Gray (1839).
2. **Descriptions of *Pachyoliva* species in selected monographs of the late 19th century**, by [2.1.] Weinkauff (1878), [2.2.] Hidalgo (1879), and [2.3.] Tryon (1883). These sources were selected because on one hand, they represent the definitions into which the original diagnoses of the two species had been developed based on apparently unambiguous criteria (Weinkauff, Hidalgo). On the other hand, they include an example for the alternative view that denied significance to these criteria due to the abundance of what seemed to be intermediate forms, and which recognized only one species, *O. columellaris* (Tryon).
3. **Identification of *Pachyoliva* species in more recent keys**, by [3.1.] Olsson (1956), [3.2.] Burch & Burch (1963), and Keen [3.3.] (1971). To my knowledge, these are the only identification keys published after 1950 that cover all members of the genus *Olivella* in the tropical east Pacific.

In the quotations below, the text appears exactly as in the original; any explanatory addition I made appears in [brackets]. Translations from German, Spanish, and Latin are mine.

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1. Original diagnoses of the two *Pachyoliva* species

1.1. *Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris*

Quoted from page 34 of the Appendix of **G.B. Sowerby**, *A Catalogue of the Shells contained in the Collection of the late Earl of Tankerville, arranged according to the Lamarckian Conchological System; together with an Appendix, containing Descriptions of many new Species*. London, E.J. Sterling 1825.

2333. OLIVA COLUMELLARIS

O. testâ oblongâ, depressâ, fuscâ, apice, basi, fasciisque duabus albidis; labio columellari albo, incrassato, calloso; callo supernè inter superiorem labii externi partem et spiram interposito; plicâ unicâ ad basim internam columellae; aperturâ supernè acutâ, subtus effusâ, margine albido; operculo tenni, lanceolato, corneo. Long. 6/16 lat. 3/10 unc.

Obs. The singularly incrassated, callous upper part of the inner lip separating the spire from the upper part of the aperture, gives to this shell a very extraordinary appearance, and forms the characteristic feature of the species. The inside of the aperture is dark brown, with a single, nearly central yellowish band.

Note the emphasis Sowerby puts on the strongly developed callus as the defining character of the species.

1.2. *Olivella (Pachyoliva) semistriata*

Quoted from page 130 of **J.E. Gray**, *Molluscous Animals, and their Shells*, in **J. Richardson, N.A. Vigors, G.T. Lay, E.T. Bennett, R. Owen, J.E. Gray, W. Buckland, G.B. Sowerby**, *The Zoology of Captain Beechey's Voyage*. London, Henry G. Bohn 1839.

OLIVA SEMISTRATA. t. 36. f. 10.

Shell ovate, lanceolate, bluish grey; spire conical, acute, rather produced, smooth, with an obscure band near the suture; last whorl closely concentrically striated on the hinder half, with a white central band; anterior belt, narrow, white. Mouth lanceolate; outer lip expanded in front; inner lip callous, extending up to the upper suture, with an obscure oblique fold, producing a single protuberance in front; canal wide; throat black; operculum horny, lanceolate. Axis 9; diam. 3½; mouth 6 lines.

Among all *Olivae* described by Gray (1839), striae on the “hinder half” of the last whorl are mentioned only for *Olivella semistriata* which is named for this distinguishing character. Intriguingly, Gray separated *Agaronia* from *Oliva* because the former has neither eyes nor tentacles, whereas in the latter “eyes are placed near the tip of the tentacles” which are “rather long” (Gray 1839, p. 129). The fact that he included the tentacle-less *Olivella semistriata* in *Oliva* suggests that he mistook the elongated lateral appendages of the propodium for tentacles.

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2. Descriptions of *Pachyoliva* species in selected monographs of the late 19th century

In the species descriptions in his authoritative monograph, Weinkauff (1878) notes no unambiguous differences in shape – he calls shells of both *Pachyoliva* species “elongate-ovate” – but lists “longitudinal slightly curved striae” on the upper body whorl for *O. semistriata* and the “strongly callous inner lip” for *O. columellaris* as important characters. His drawings, however, are unclear with respect to the striae on the body whorl which seem to be visible in the apertural views of both species. Speaking of *O. columellaris*, he comments (p. 117): “Very easily recognizable species. *O. attenuata* is perhaps an immature stage in which the inner lip callus has not formed yet.” Weinkauff modified this conclusion in a subsequent chapter (printing technologies of the time did not allow for easy corrections once the type was set). On page 145, he actually evaluates *O. attenuata* in a separate entry and writes: “This certainly is nothing else but a small variety of *O. semistriata* and not of *O. columellaris*, as I had stated on p. 117. Among numerous specimens [that I examined] ... there are a few which, if inspected under incident light, show the striae typical of the main form.” Evidently, he considered striae on the upper body whorl decisive in cases in which the callus did not provide a conclusive argument.

Hidalgo’s accounts (1879) resemble that of Weinkauff (1878); most interesting are the “*Observ.[ations]*” which Hidalgo adds to his species descriptions. Having described *O. semistriata*, he states: “The striae on the last whorl occupy its upper half. Two whitish transverse bands do not always exist, sometimes they are absent or only one is observed”. Obviously, he found the structural character (striae) more reliable than coloration. Following the description of *O. columellaris*, he specifies how the species can be distinguished in practice: “This species [*O. columellaris*] is quite similar to the previous one [*O. semistriata*] but is distinguished well from the latter due to the lack of striae on the upper part of the last whorl ... *Olivella columellaris* also has more compact callus on the columella, a shorter and more callous spire, and a blackish line in the basal zone. The remaining characters are very similar to those of *Olivella semistriata* ...” (p. 83).

Tryon (1883) followed Weinkauff (1878) closely – not closely enough, though, to recognize both *O. columellaris* and *O. semistriata* as proper species. His approach is characterized by the statement (p. 62) that “Dr. J.E. Gray proposed elaborate series of genera and subgenera of the Olivinae; most of them, whilst serving to separate specified types, failing entirely to furnish distinctive characters for other species which are intermediate in form.” Apparently aware of such intermediate forms, Tryon included *O. semistriata* GRAY, *O. affinis* MARRAT, and *O. attenuata* REEVE in *O. columellaris* SOWERBY. Surprisingly, longitudinal striae on the upper part of the body whorl are part of his definition of the inclusive species, although his figures show this character only for the “type” *O. semistriata*.

Shell lengths given by the three authors are 22 mm (Weinkauff) and 14 mm (Hidalgo) for *O. semistriata*, 19 mm (Weinkauff) and 15 mm (Hidalgo) for *O. columellaris*, and 15 mm for Tryon’s inclusive *O. columellaris*.

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2.1. H.C. Weinkauff, 1878

Die Gattung Oliva (Systematisches Conchylien-Cabinet von Martini und Chemnitz, Vol. 5 Abt. 1), Nürnberg, Bauer & Raspe. Quoted text is from pp. 116–118 and 145, lists of synonyms omitted; drawings are reproduced from *Tafel 31*.

88. *Oliva (Olivella) columellaris* Sowerby. Taf. 31. Fig. 1. 2.

Testa elongato-ovata, plus minusve mucronata, albida zonis spiralibus tribus caerulescente-cinereis picta; spira breviscula, acuta, anfractibus 5 callo-convexis, albis, suturis anguste-canaliculatis; apex parvus, acutus, candidus; apertura superne angusta, inferne ampla, intus intense purpurea, albido fasciata; columella callosa, superne „usque ad spiram crasse callosa, basi obsolete uniplicata,“ labrum superne leviter incrassatum, tenuissime emarginatum, inferne tenue; area basalis non partita, callosa; sinus basalis latus.

Long. 19, diam. maj. 11, apert. 13 Mm.

Schale länglich-eiförmig, mehr oder weniger kurz zugespitzt, weisslich mit drei blau-grauen Spiralzonen, woran die eine sich noch zuweilen teilt; Spira klein, spitz, besteht aus 5 schnell zunehmenden Umgängen – meistens ist nur der Abstand zwischen dem vorletzten und dritten Umgang ein starker – die durch sehr enge Nahtrinnen getrennt sind, sie sind convex und callös, besonders die beiden letzten; Embryonalende klein und spitz, 3 glashelle Umgänge bildend. Mündung oben eng, fast an der Spindel anliegend, unten weit, innen tief pupurfarben, fast schwarz mit weisslicher Binde; Spindel stark callös belegt, besonders oben dick und zuweilen bis über den unteren Theil der Spira übertretend, wodurch der vorletzte Umgang mit verdickt wird, glänzend weiss, an der Basis steht eine undeutliche Falte; Mundrand oben leicht verdickt unten dünn aber stumpf; Basalparthie ungetheilt, fast ganz callös verdickt; Basalsinus weit und ziemlich flach.

Sehr leicht kenntliche Art. *O. attenuata* ist vielleicht der Jugendzustand, bei dem der Spindelcallus noch nicht ausgebildet ist.

88. *Oliva (Olivella) semistriata* Gray. Taf. 31. Fig. 3. 4.

Testa elongato-ovata, semilirata, liris longitudinalibus, leviter arcuatis, „anfractus ultimi dimidium posticum occupantibus,“ albida zonis binis spiralibus cinereo-caerulescentibus picta; spira acuminata, anfractibus 5 vix convexis, sutura angusta; apex parvus, acutus, candidus; apertura supernae angusta, inferne ampla, intus ferruginea, albido fasciata; columella arcuata, late labiata et tenue callosa, alba superne fusco maculata, inferne uniplicata; labrum acutum, tenue, superne angustissime emarginatum; area basalis non partita, albocallosa; sinus basalis latus.

Long. 22, lata, 10, apert. 14 Mm.

Schale länglich-eiförmig, unten glatt, oben der Länge nach mit leicht gebogenen Leistchen geziert, die etwa die Hälfte des Hauptumgangs einnehmen, weisslich mit zweien blaulich aschfarbigen, oft ins bräunliche fallenden Zonen geziert; Spira lang ausgezogen, spitz, besteht aus 5 kaum convexen Umgängen, die durch feine, scharfgeschnittene Nahtrinnen, getrennt werden; Embryonalende klein und spitz, besteht aus 3 glasshellen Umgängen. Mündung oben eng, fast anliegend, unten sehr weit, oben schmall gelippt und dünn callös, glänzend weiss und oben mit einem bräunlichen Flecken geziert; Mundrand dünn und scharf, oben sehr eng eingeschnitten; Basalparthie ungetheilt, durch weissen Callus verdickt; Basalsinus weit und flach.

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133. *Oliva (Olivella) attenuata* Reeve. Taf. 37. Fig. 3. 4.

„Testa ovata, basin versus latiuscula, apicem versus peculiariter acuminata, columella subarcuata, vix plicata, callosa; pellucido-cornea, fusco-rufo late bifasciata.” (Reeve.)

Dies ist sicher nicht anderes, als eine kleine Varietät der *O. semistriata* nicht wie ich p. 117 angeführt, der *O. columellaris*. Unter zahlreichen Exemplaren aus der Loebbeck'schen Sammlung, die Dr. Lische von Californien erhalten hatte, sind einzelne, die bei auffallendem Licht die Streifung der Hauptform zeigen. Da die Exemplare constant kleiner sind und in der Verbreitung eine grosse Lücke zwischen Peru und Californien vorhanden, so mag die Art bis zur Ausfüllung der Lücke als solche bestehen bleiben; ich kann mir aber eine deutsche Beschreibung ersparen und auf die der *O. semistriata* verweisen. Die Binde ist etwas deutlicher, als bei dieser Art.

[Tafel 31] Fig. 1, 2, *Oliva (Olivella) columellaris* Sowerby. Fig. 3, 4, *O. (Olivella) semistriata* Gray.

2.2. J.G. Hidalgo, 1879

Moluscos del Viaje al Pacifico Verificado de 1862 a 1865 por una Comision de Naturalistas Enviada por el Gobierno Español, Madrid, Miguel Ginesta. Quotations are from pp. 81–83, lists of synonyms omitted below.

Olivella semistriata Gray.

Testa oblongo-conico, plerumque tenuis, nitida, subpellucida, lævigata, ultimo anfractu superne striis incrementi, plus minus validis, confertissime sculpto; cæruleo-plumbea, albido sæpe bifasciata, fasciis angustis, subdistantibus, spira baltioque basali albis; spira callosa, exserta, conica, sensim attenuata, apice acuto, subpapillari; sutura parum obliqua, spadicea; anfr. 8, planati, ultimus paulo convexus, inferne balteo simplici latiusculo ornatus; apertura subobliqua, oblongo-triangularis, basi late emarginata, intus concolor, labro tenui, margine acuto, convexo, columella obliqua, sæpe rectiuscula, omnino albo-callosa, callo ætate crassiusculo, inferne plica brevi arcuata, planulata, instructo. Long 14, lat. 5½ millim. Apertura intus 6½ mill. longa, 2½ lata.

Concha oblongo-cónica, por lo comun delgada, brillante, un poco trasparente, lisa, con numerosas estrias de crecimiento, más ó ménos marcadas, en la parte superior de la ultima vuelta; color azulado-

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plomizo, con dos fajas blanquecinas transversales, estrechas y algo separadas; la espira y la zona de la base de color blanco; espira callosa, saliente cónica, sensiblemente estrachada hácia el ápice, el cual es puntiagudo y algo papilar; sutura poco oblicua, de color de castaña; vueltas de espira en número de 8, aplanadas, la última poco convexa, con la zona de la base sencilla y algo ancha; abertura un poco oblicua, oblongo-triangular, con la escotadura de la base ancha, y la coloracion de dentro igual á la del exterior; borde derecho delgado, cortante y convexo en el margen; columnilla oblicua, casi siempre algo recta, provista en toda su extension de una callosidad blanca, la cual es un poco gruesa en los individuos adultos y presenta en la parte inferior un pliegue corto, arqueado y aplanado.

Hab. — Chinandega, América central (Espada).

Est. — Recogidos algunos ejemplares en la arena, á poca profundidad.

Observ. Las estrias de la última vuelta ocupan la mitad superior de la misma. No siempre existen las dos fajas transversales blanquecinas, pues faltan algunas veces ó sólo se observa una; la superior esta colocada á poca distancia de la sutura y la inferior ocupa próximamente el centro de la última vuelta. La callosidad de la columnilla se continúa por arriba sobre la espira, siguiendo las vueltas de ésta, pero dejando á descubierto la sutura.

***Olivella columellaris* Sowerby.**

Testa ovato-conica, subdepressa, plerumque tenuis, nitida, subpellucida, lævigata; cæruleo-plumbea, spira atque fasciis binis transversis, subdistantibus, lutescenti-albidis balteoque basali albido superme linea fusca ornato; spira exsertiuscula, conica, valde callosa, sensim attenuata, apice acuto, subpapillari; sutura parum obliqua, sæpe spadicea; anfr. 6, planati, ultimo paulo convexus, basi subdilatus, balteo simplici latiusculo ornatus; apertura subobliqua, oblongo-triangularis, basi late emarginata, intus fusca, medio albido unifasciata, labro tenui, margine acuto, convexo, ætate obtusiusculo, superne vix appresso, columella obliqua, rectiuscula, omnino albo-callosa, callo ætate crassissimo, inferne plica brevi arcuata, planulata, instructo. Long. 15, lat 6½ millim. Apertura intus 8 mill. longa. 3 lata.

Concha oval-cónica, algo deprimida, casi siempre delgada, brillante, un poco trasparente, lisa; color azulado-plomizo con la espira y dos fajas transversales, algo separadas, de un amarillento-blanquecino, y la zona de la base de color blanquecino con una línea negruzca en la parte superior; espira algo saliente, cónica, muy callosa, sensiblemente estrechada hácia el ápice, el cual es puntiagudo y algo papilar; sutura poco oblicua, casi siempre de color de castaña; vueltas de espira en número de 6, aplanadas; la última poco convexa, algo más ancha en la base, en la cual hay una zona ligeramente saliente, sencilla y un poco ancha; abertura algo oblicua, oblongo-triangular, con la escotadura de la base ancha, negruzca por dentro, con una faja blanquecina en el medio; borde derecho sencillo, cortante y convexo en el margen, algo obtuso en los individuos adultos y con una ligerísima depresion en la parte superior; columnilla oblicua, algo recta, provista en toda su extension de una callosidad blanca, la cual es muy gruesa en la edad adulta y presenta inferiormente un pliegue corto, arqueado y aplanado.

Hab. — Paita, Perú (Paz).

Est. — En fondo de arena, á 5 ó 6 brazas. Poco abundante.

Observ. Esta especie es muy semejante á la anterior; pero se distingue bien de ella por la falta de estrias en la parte superior de la última vuelta, y la depresion algo marcada de esta última. La *Olivella columellaris* tiene tambien más gruesa la callosidad de la columnilla, más corta y callosa la espira y una línea negruzca en la zona de la base. Los demas caracteres son muy semejantes á los de la *Olivella*

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semistriata Gray, pues las dos zonas transversales estan colocadas del mismo modo y la callosidad de la columella se extiende por toda la espiro sin invadir nunca la sutura. En la última vuelta se perciben á veces líneas longitudinales blanquecinas, paralelas al borde derecho, y que indican los diversos crecimientos de la concha.

2.3. G.W. Tryon, 1883

Manual of Conchology; Structural and Systematic, Vol. 5: Marginellidae, Olividae, Colimnellidae, Philadelphia, Published by the author. The quoted text is from p. 67; the drawings are reproduced from *Plate 15*.

Genus *Olivella*, Swainson

O. columellaris, Sowb. Pl. 15, figs 70–73.

Accuminately ovate, the spire exerted, base broadly effused; columellar lip with heavy callus extending to the top of the body-whorl; commencing at the suture are a number of close, fine, longitudinal striae, which extend longitudinally to near the centre of the body-whorl, where they become obsolete, and the rest of the whorl is polished; spire and fasciole white, body-whorl almost covered by three chestnut or plum-colored bands, the two dividing interspaces of yellowish white being quite narrow. Length, 12–15 mill.

Payta, Peru, in fine sand at low water (Cuming)

W. Columbia; Panama

O. semistriata, Gray (fig. 71), *O. attenuata*, Reeve (fig. 72), and *O. affinis*, Marrat (fig. 73), are synonyms.

70. *Olivella columellaris*, Sowb. 71. *Olivella semistriata*, Gray (= *columellaris*).
72. *Olivella attenuata*, Reeve (= *columellaris*). 73. *Olivella affinis*, Marr. (= *columellaris*).

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3. Identification of *Pachyoliva* species in modern keys

Olsson (1956) is the only one among the modern authors quoted below who describes the unique structure of the propodium in *Pachyoliva*, although he makes no comment on the function of the lateral appendages. Intriguingly, he also is the only author who does not mention the striations on the body whorl in *O. semistriata*, which suggests that he found this feature not a constant and reliable trait. Consequently, he distinguishes *O. semistriata* and *O. columellaris* only on the basis of shell shape (especially shape of the spire) and the amount of callus formed. Unlike other authors, Olsson does not mention shell coloration, which in fact is variable and provides no useful criteria for species identification. Olsson considers *Oliva affinis* MARRAT and *Oliva attenuata* REEVE synonyms of *O. semistriata* GRAY.

Burch & Burch (1963) distinguish the two species based on shell shape (especially shape of the spire), the amount of callus formation, and the presence of striae on the body whorl. They discuss shell coloration, but caution that “in the Olividae, the worker will immediately be confronted with specimens that are certainly of the same species with some having one band, others 2 or 3 bands, and others with no bands. ... the multitude of names given to species in this family is because authors have failed to consider variation caused by races. The tendency of a single species to appear in numerous color forms is also a contributing factor.” (p. 1).

Keen (1971) follows Burch & Burch (1963), emphasizing the “distinctive” striae in *O. semistriata*. She considers *Oliva attenuata* REEVE, *Olivina semisulcata* GRAY, and *Oliva affinis* MARRAT synonyms of *O. semistriata* GRAY.

Both Keen (1971) and Burch & Burch (1963) report shell lengths of 15 mm for *O. semistriata* and 14 mm for *O. columellaris*. Olsson (1956) gives no measures but *O. columellaris* is 10% shorter than *O. semistriata* on his plates.

3.1. A.A. Olsson, 1956

Studies on the Genus *Olivella*, *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia* **108**, 155–225. It is this work in which the subgenus *Pachyoliva* was established. The quoted text is found on pp. 167 and 201–203. Olsson includes information on synonyms, structure of the radulae, use of the shells by ancient cultures, etc., which I omit here. Remarks on soft body structure in *O. semistriata* apply to the entire subgenus (p. 201).

Key to the Subgenera of *Olivella* on Shell Characteristics

AA. The callous formation along the parietal wall is strongly developed, extending above the end of the aperture towards the upper suture of the penultimate whorl.

Ba. Pillar wall concave or deeply excavated by corrosion, the lirations of the inner lip if present, cut off sharply on their inner ends.

C. Pillar and parietal wall covered fully by a thick deposit of callus. No pillar or parietal lirations at any stage. Subgenus *Pachyoliva*, new subgenus.

To *Pachyoliva* belong two of the commonest *Olivella* in the Panamic-Pacific faunal area, *O. columellaris* and *semistriata*, often appearing in countless numbers along certain sandy beaches. In both species, the inner lip is covered with a layer of callus which in *columellaris* may become excessively thickened by it.

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Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris (Sowerby).

... A heavily calloused species with a short, knob-like spire and a large body whorl. Immature specimens have a thin shell with a wide, shallow, siphonal notch and a strongly twisted keel at the end of the columella; the parietal callus begins to form at an early stage at the upper end of aperture and rapidly spreads upward towards the suture which, however, remains open. ... Range – Coast of northwestern Peru ... and possibly northward to Panama and the Gulf of California.

Olivella (Pachyoliva) semistriata (Gray).

[synonyms listed are *Oliva affinis* Marrat, and *Oliva attenuata* Reeve] This is a more northerly species than *columellaris*, with a higher, more slender and more sharply pointed spire, and less heavily calloused. ... Animal; lateral margins of the propodium with large, tentacle-like appendages; color generally blackish, the edges of the foot margined with white. ... Range – Gulf of California southward to northern Peru.

3.2. J.Q. Burch & R.L. Burch, 1963

Genus *Olivella* in Eastern Pacific, *The Nautilus* 77, 1–8 plus three plates. The quotations are from p. 5. Note the restricted geographical range to which this key applies; not the complete genus *Olivella* is covered.

1 Parietal callus extending past aperture to or near suture

2 Pillar wall concave or deeply excavated; lirae of inner lip if present cut off sharply at inner ends

3 Pillar and parietal wall covered fully by a thick callus; no pillar or parietal lirae *Pachyoliva* Olsson, 1956

4 Callus with short knob-like spire and large body whorl; spire and fasciole white; body whorl with 3 broad brown or bluish-gray bands; 14 mm. (fig. 8) *columellaris* (Sowerby, 1825)

4 Pillar and color pattern similar, but with higher, slenderer and sharply pointed spire, and less calloused; apical ½ of body whorl with faint series of vertical striae; 15 mm. (fig. 20) *semistriata* (Gray, 1839)

3.3. A.M. Keen, 1971

Sea Shells of Tropical West America, Stanford, Stanford University Press. Quotations are from pp. 626 and 631–632. Due to the geographical range to which this key applies, not the complete genus *Olivella* is included.

Genus *Olivella* Swainson, 1840

1 Columellar callus extending above end of aperture

What can we learn from confusing *Olivella columellaris* and *O. semistriata* (Olivellidae, Gastropoda), two key species in panamic sandy beach ecosystems?

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2 Columellar wall partly removed from within, leaving any lirations sharply cut off at inner end

3 Lirations wanting, columellar wall smooth. Subgenus *Pachyoliva* Olsson, 1956

1394. *Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris* (Sowerby, 1825). Type of the subgenus, this has a heavy callus, short, knob-like spire, and a large body whorl. The spire and fasciole are white and the body whorl has three broad brown or bluish-gray spiral bands. About 14 mm long. Nicaragua to Peru.

1395. *Olivella (Pachyoliva) semistriata* (Gray, 1839) (Synonyms: *Oliva attenuata* Reeve, 1850; *Olivina semisulcata* Gray, 1858; *Oliva affinis* Marrat in Sowerby, 1871). This has a higher and more slender spire than *O. columellaris*, and a faint series of vertical striae at the upper margin of the body whorl is distinctive. Length, 15 mm; diameter, 7 mm. The Gulf of California to northern Peru.